

What Industry Wants from Academia in Software Modeling

In this survey, the goal is to understand the challenges that practitioners face with in industry about software modeling. We consider the software modeling challenges in terms of a set of well-established software modeling categories and the survey intends to shed light on the practical problems about each of these modeling categories.

The survey is expected to take 2-7 minutes at most and the results of the survey will be analysed to determine any potential collaborations between practitioners and academia in software modeling. Also, a paper that discusses the survey results is planned to be written and published in a well-regarded journal/conference.

No identifying information will be collected and all participants shall remain anonymous. Collected data are planned to be published as a research article.

By clicking through the consent statement and submitting the completed survey, individuals are indicating their willingness to participate.
We really appreciate your time and input.

If you have any questions about the survey, please contact Dr. Mert Ozkaya (mozkaya@cse.yeditepe.edu.tr).

1. Accept and continue

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No *Stop filling out this form.*

Profile Questions

2. Which country do you work in?*Mark only one oval.*

- Australia
- Belgium
- Brazil
- Canada
- China
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- India
- Italy
- Mexico
- Portugal
- Russia
- Spain
- Sweden
- The Netherlands
- Turkey
- UK
- USA
- Other: _____

3. Which industry(ies) do you develop software products for?

Check all that apply.

- Automotive and Transportation
- Computer
- Consumer Electronics
- Defense/Military & Aviation
- Electrical Utilities
- Energy
- Finance and Accounting
- Government
- Healthcare and Biomedical
- Media
- Research
- Software Outsourcing
- Supply Chain
- IT and Telecommunications
- Other: _____

Managing Language Complexity

Concerned with the issues such as languages' notational complexity, notational expressiveness, the extensibility of the language notation set, languages' tool support for large and complex problems.

4. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Managing Language Complexity", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Stop filling out this form.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Managing Language Complexity-2

Concerned with the issues such as languages' notational complexity, notational expressiveness, the extensibility of the language notation set, languages' tool support for large and complex problems.

5. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Managing Language Complexity" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The languages' small base notation set for the modeling of complex problems
- The languages' complex notation set that is not easy to understand and use
- The challenges on modifying the language syntax and semantics for the domain-specific problems
- The languages' weak tool support for managing large and complex software models (e.g., sub-diagramming)
- Other: _____

Extending Modeling Languages

Concerned with the issues such as extending the language with new notations or new semantics, modifying the existing semantics, and updating the tools for the new semantics.

6. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Extending Modeling Languages", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Skip to question 8.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Extending Modeling Languages-2

Concerned with the issues such as extending the language with new notations or new semantics, modifying the existing semantics, and updating the tools for the new semantics.

7. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Extending Modeling Languages" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The challenges on extending the language with some new notations
- The challenges on adding some new semantics without causing any inconsistencies
- The challenges on modifying the existing language semantics
- The challenges on updating the language tools for the newly added (or modified) semantics
- Other: _____

Domain-specific Modeling Environments

Concerned with the issues such as evolving the domain-specific language (DSL) tools (e.g., editors, code generators, and analysers), using multiple DSLs together on the same software model, and using different versions of the same DSLs on the same software model.

8. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Domain-specific Modeling Environments", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Skip to question 10.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Domain-specific Modeling Environments-2

Concerned with the issues such as evolving the domain-specific language (DSL) tools (e.g., editors, code generators, and analysers), using multiple DSLs together on the same software model, and using different versions of the same DSLs on the same software model.

9. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Domain-specific Modeling Environments" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers ?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The challenges on evolving the DSL tools (editors, checkers, analysers, and code generators) with some new domain requirements
- The challenges on using and integrating multiple DSLs together for the same software model
- The challenges on using different versions of the DSLs on the same software model
- Other: _____

Developing Formal Modeling Languages

Concerned with the issues such as translating software models into formal models that can be used for rigorous model-checking, integrating DSLs with translators for formal models, ensuring the correct translation for formal models, and the steep learning curve due to the formal modeling.

10. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Developing Formal Modeling Languages", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Skip to question 12.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Developing Formal Modeling Languages-2

Concerned with the issues such as translating software models into formal models that can be used for rigorous model-checking, integrating DSLs with translators for formal models, ensuring the correct translation for formal models, and the steep learning curve due to the formal modeling.

11. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Developing Formal Modeling Languages" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers ?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The challenges on devising the algorithms/rules for translating software models in any formalisms that support model-checking
- The challenges on ensuring the correct translation into the formalisms that support model-checking
- The challenges on integrating the existing DSLs with the translators for model-checking
- The steep learning curve due to the use of formalisms
- Other: _____

Analysing Models

Concerned with the issues such as the formal model analysis, model simulation, and model-based testing techniques.

12. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Analysing Models", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Skip to question 14.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Analysing Models-2

Concerned with the issues such as the formal model analysis, model simulation, and model-based testing techniques.

13. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Analysing Models" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers ?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The challenges on the formal (i.e., rigorous) model analysis
- The challenges on the model simulation
- The challenges on the model-based testing techniques
- Other: _____

Supporting Separation of Design Concerns

Concerned with the issues such as multiple-viewpoints modeling, the consistencies of different software viewpoint models, using DSLs for creating new modeling viewpoints, and using aspect-oriented software modeling techniques.

14. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Supporting Separation of Design Concerns", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Skip to question 16.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Supporting Separation of Design Concerns-2

Concerned with the issues such as multiple-viewpoints modeling, the consistencies of different software viewpoint models, using DSLs for creating new modeling viewpoints, and using aspect-oriented software modeling techniques.

15. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Supporting Separation of Design Concerns" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers ?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The challenges on modeling software systems from different viewpoints
- The challenges on analysing the relationships between different software viewpoint models
- The challenges on using DSLs for creating and using domain-specific modeling viewpoints
- The challenges on using aspect-oriented software modeling techniques
- Other: _____

Transforming Models

Concerned with the issues such as model refactoring, model refinement, model abstraction, the synchronization transformation, ensuring the consistent transformation between source and target models, and testing the model transformations.

16. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Transforming Models", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Skip to question 18.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Transforming Models-2

Concerned with the issues such as model refactoring, model refinement, model abstraction, the synchronization transformation, ensuring the consistent transformation between source and target models, and testing the model transformations.

17. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Transforming Models" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers ?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The challenges on model refactoring (improving the software structure model without changing its behaviour)
- The challenges on model refinement (adding further details to the existing software model)
- The challenges on model abstraction (reducing the software model complexity without damaging its precision)
- The challenges on ensuring the consistent transformation (the source and target models are consistent with each other)
- The challenges on the synchronization transformation (a change in one model triggers a change on another model)
- The challenges on testing the model transformations
- Other: _____

Managing Models

Concerned with the issues such as maintaining the model repositories, model versioning, model dependencies, and model realisation.

18. Indicate the level of challenges that you face in the category of "Managing Models", in which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers in academia.

Mark only one oval.

- No challenges at all *Skip to question 20.*
- Some challenges
- Average level of challenges
- Many challenges
- Lots of challenges

Managing Models-2

Concerned with the issues such as maintaining the model repositories, model versioning, model dependencies, and model realisation.

19. What type(s) of challenges do you face in the category of "Managing Models" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers ?

Check all that apply.

- No challenges considered.
- The challenges on maintaining the model repository
- The challenges on model versioning
- The challenges on managing the model dependency relationships
- The challenges on model realisation
- The challenges on using the modeling tools that allow for extending the language meta-models for model manipulations
- Other: _____

Other Modeling Categories

20. List below the challenges that you face in "Other Modeling Categories" on which you would consider collaborations with software modeling researchers (please separate multiple items by commas)

Concluding

21. Feel free to indicate any comments or suggestions that you may have:
